

oil (5%) was applied to seedlings 2 h before inoculation.

Increasing the number of insects increased infection from 50 to 95% in susceptible ADT31 and from 5 to 35% in resistant TNAU831520 (see figure). In

ADT31, neem oil significantly reduced infection rates when 1 GLH was used for inoculation. A similar reduction was observed with inoculation using 3 or 5 GLH/plant.

All treated plants of TNAU831520 were free of infection when one GLH was used for inoculation. Neem oil reduced infection to 10% in resistant plants inoculated using 3 or 5 insects. □

Some pathological and physiological diseases of rice in Punjab

M.S. Kang and I. Singh, Plant Disease Clinic (PDC), Plant Pathology Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

In Punjab, rice is grown as a wet season crop May-Oct. With the release of high-yielding varieties IR8, Jaya, and PR106, the area under rice cultivation has increased from 258,000 ha in 1966-67 to 1,703,000 ha in 1985-86.

Samples of diseased rice plants received for diagnosis by PDC 1980-85 are shown in the table. Bacterial blight appeared in 71% of the samples in 1980, then its incidence declined to 1985, when it increased to 44% samples infected.

Sheath rot has threatened the most

Diseases in samples of rice in Punjab, India, 1980-85.

Disease	Diseased samples (%)					
	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985
Bacterial blight	71	28	13	10	10	44
Sheath rot	3	19	19	27	6	2
False smut	5	1	5	8	7	2
Sheath blight	4	7	5	3	3	1
Bacterial leaf streak	3	0	0	0	0	4
Acid rain	0	0	0	0	1	2
Zn deficiency	13	17	50	28	10	8
Fe deficiency	0	6	0	15	5	4
N deficiency	0	16	3	8	8	3

popular variety PR106. False smut has recently gained importance, with infection in 1-7.5% of the samples. Stem rot caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, considered to be very severe before the introduction of high-yielding varieties,

was conspicuously absent from the samples received. This could be due to rice - wheat rotation. Bacterial leaf streak appeared occasionally in 1980 and 1985. Blast and brown leaf spot seem unimportant now. □

Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of carbofuran against whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

G. Liu and R.M. Wilkins, Agricultural Biology Department. University of Newcastle upon Tyne. Newcastle upon Tyne NE1 7RU, United Kingdom

We evaluated the antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of systemic insecticide carbofuran against WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath). Three treatments were tested: topically treating WBPH with carbofuran solutions in acetone, using a no-soil root-zone application to susceptible glasshouse-grown TN1 rice plants, and treating leaves of potted TN1 plants with acetone solutions using a fine brush. Recently emerged (3-5 d)

Table 1. Antifeeding effect of carbofuran on macropterous WBPH females.^a Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom.

Treatment method	Concentration	Quantity of amino acids in honeydew ^b (µg dry weight/female per 24 h)	Antifeeding response (%)
Leaf (µg/cm ²)	0.159	28.6 a	54.7
	0.079	33.7 a	46.9
	0.016	43.8 b	31.3
	0.0	63.9 c	
Topical (ng/female)	0.1	23.3 a	78.1
	0.02	34.5 a	67.6
	0.01	54.1 b	48.6
	0.002	77.9 c	25.7
	0.0	105.6 d	
Root zone (µM)	2.0	18.5 a	68.4
	1.5	23.0 b	59.7
	1.0	30.9 c	47.4
	0.5	36.2 d	36.8
	0.1	46.9 e	17.5
	0.0	56.8 f	

^a Within a treatment method, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P = 0.05 by Duncan's multiple range test. No mortality was observed with any concentration (i.e., less than 5% mortality). Temperature 26 ± 1°. ^b Mean of 3 replications: quantity of amino acids in honeydew measured colorimetrically using glutamic acid as standard.

macropterous females were used in all experiments, with 3 replications.

Antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of carbofuran on WBPH was measured as an antifeeding response:

$$\text{Antifeeding response (\%)} = \frac{B-A}{B} 100$$

where A = quantity of honeydew excreted by carbofuran-treated WBPH adults and B = quantity of honeydew excreted by untreated WBPH adults.

As honeydew is produced by a WBPH population, response can be represented as the means of carbofuran concentration causing 50% reduction in feeding (AFC₅₀), calculated by probit regression.

Table 2. Calculated probit regressions and LC₅₀ or AFC₅₀ values for responses of macropterous WBPH females^a treated with carbofuran. Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom.

Treatment	Response	Regression equation ^b	LC ₅₀ or AFC ₅₀	Fiducial limits	Efficiency index ^c
Leaf (µg/cm ²)	Mortality	$y = 2.81 + 3.11x$	0.51	0.44-0.58	4.8
	Antifeed	$y = 4.38 + 0.60x$	0.11	0.05-0.23	
Topical (ng/g)	Mortality	$y = 1.96 + 2.86x$	865.6	656-1126	128.9
	Antifeed	$y = 4.17 + 0.85x$	6.72	4.48-9.70	
Root zone (µM)	Mortality	$y = 2.19 + 2.97x$	8.82	7.45-10.45	9.8
	Antifeed	$y = 3.99 + 1.05x$	0.90	0.64-1.27	

^aMean female body weight = 1.34 mg. *y* indicates probit, *x* indicates log (concentration); units are µg/cm² in leaf, ng/g in topical and micromolar (µM) in root-zone treatments. ^cEfficiency index = LC₅₀/AFC₅₀.

Corresponding toxicities (LC₅₀) were determined at 24 h for leaf (indirect) and topical (direct) treatments and at 48 h for root-zone (indirect) application. As contact of insects with carbofuran

increased, antifeeding response at lower concentrations became more evident (shown comparatively at the 50% level by the efficiency index) (Tables 1 and 2). □

Rodent damage in Punjab ricefields, Pakistan

A.A. Khan, *Vertebrate Pest Control Laboratory, Pakistan Agricultural Research Council, P.O. Box 8401, Karachi University Campus, Karachi 32, Pakistan*

Preharvest rice crop losses in Pakistan are due primarily to three species of field rats. The lesser bandicoot or Indian mole rat *Bandicota bengalensis* is the most common pest. This species cuts the

Estimated rodent damage and yield reduction in standing rice in major rice-growing areas of Punjab, Pakistan.

District and site	Damage (%/ha)	Area sampled (ha)	Tiller damage (%)	Yield reduction (%)
<i>Sheikhupura</i>				
Ferozwala	2.72	22.06	9.99	7.40
Sheikhupura	2.17	26.11	6.29	3.54
Nankana	5.55	13.17	24.37	22.40
<i>Sialkot</i>				
Pasroor	5.27	25.50	22.40	20.35
Sialkot	2.83	24.90	11.74	9.23
Daska	4.04	25.30	17.04	14.75
<i>Gujranwala</i>				
Hafizabad	3.95	25.30	16.67	14.37
Wazirabad	5.32	24.49	21.72	19.64
Gujranwala	3.63	23.48	14.22	11.81

Rodent damage to standing rice in 3 districts of Punjab, Pakistan.

tillers of the rice crop between nursery and seed hardening stages and also hoards grain. The short-tailed mole rat *Nesokia indica* and the soft-furred rat *Millardia meltada* are also important rodent pests.

We surveyed crop losses to rats in three major rice-growing districts of Punjab: Sheikhupura, Gujranwala, and Sialkot. A multistage sampling technique was used to select subdistricts, villages, and farms; 468 fields on 52 farms were examined and about 100 hills measured for rat injury in each field 2 wk before harvest. Damage was widely distributed (see figure) — 94.1% of the fields surveyed had damaged tillers. In 78.3%, damage averaged 1.7%;

in 15.7%, damage averaged 2.6%. About 52% of the dry fields had rodent burrows inside. The number of burrows on a damage transect line averaged 0.52/field.

Estimated rat damage is summarized in the table. Average cumulative tiller damage was 16.1%, or 3.9%/ha. Damage in Sialkot and Gujranwala districts were similar.

Damage calculated was 15.8% for Basmati and 15.5% for IRRI-6. In Sheikhupura district, IRRI-6 and Basmati did not differ significantly in susceptibility to rat damage ($P > 0.05$). In Sialkot and Gujranwala, the difference between varieties was significant ($P < 0.05$). Varietal susceptibility within